

CNN-based Wallpaper Retrieval System

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Abstract — This paper presents a system, for image search and similarity finding using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model called ResNet50. The system leverages the NumPy and TensorFlow frameworks to efficiently process data. Unlike text based search engines this approach aims to address the issue of potentially unrelated results returned by such engines. This can often lead to frustration. Wasted time for users. Instead the proposed system employs content based image retrieval, which allows users to retrieve products based on picture queries. To achieve this a robust feature extraction algorithm is utilized to extract features from every image in the database, including the query image. By computing the similarity, between the query image and all stored photos relevant images that closely resemble the query can be obtained.

Keywords; Image Search, TensorFlow, Numpy, Deep Learning, Content based image retrieval, ResNet50.

I. INTRODUCTION

A visual search engine is a type of search engine where users can find images based on their content of using text based queries. In this kind of search engine the resulting images are determined by their similarity to the queried image. These types of search engines are highly effective compared to text based searches since they prioritize accuracy and efficiency. In this paper we introduce a method, for creating a search engine by utilizing the ResNet50 convolutional neural network in conjunction, with the NumPy and TensorFlow libraries.

With the growing prevalence of social media and various online platforms, individuals are increasingly immersed in visual content. Consequently, their inclination has shifted towards image-based search, surpassing traditional text-based queries. In the realm of e-commerce websites, this shift is particularly beneficial for efficient product discovery. In image-based search, customers initiate the process by uploading a query image, and the platform promptly presents them with visually similar images. This streamlined approach enables customers to swiftly and effortlessly find the products they desire, eliminating the need for prolonged searches based on specific keywords.

The basis of image based search, in e commerce relies on computer vision technology, which utilizes the power of machine learning and artificial intelligence to recognize and analyze the characteristics of images. This advanced technology can identify attributes like color, texture, size and shape. Compare them to similar products available on Wallpaper websites.

In our approach we heavily rely on ResNet50, a established neural network. ResNet50 plays a role as it learns features from images through convolutional and pooling layers. The output of these layers is then. Passed through a connected layer to generate a distinctive feature vector, for each image.

This method uses a variety of image datasets, from our project database to determine if the desired product exists within our system. In the context of learning preprocessing plays a role. It involves converting data into a format that can seamlessly integrate into the neural network. Preprocessing includes steps such as resizing, normalization and cropping images.

In our approach we leverage ResNet50 a neural network, to automatically extract features from images. This is achieved by applying CNN principles like pooling layers, which allow the network to learn image features on its own. The output of these layers is then. Passed through a connected layer to generate a unique feature vector for each image.

The feature vectors obtained in the step are then indexed using an indexing method. When we receive a query image we follow the process of feature extraction. Use the resulting feature vector that combines ResNet50 and CNN capabilities to search for similar images within the indexed dataset.

The final stage of this process involves organizing search results based on the similarity between the query image and other images, in our dataset. Different techniques, such, as the distance can be employed to determine the likeness, between images.

A. Nature of Convolutional neural network

A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a part of learning specifically designed to process and identify images and other types of multidimensional data. It draws inspiration from the structure and functionality of the system, which excels at recognizing objects and their patterns, in visual stimuli.

CNNs use a series of layers to extract features from input images or data. These features are then passed through connected layers, a characteristic unique to deep learning resulting in a prediction or classification. The convolutional layers are equipped with filters or kernels that convolve over the input data extracting

features like edges, lines, textures and shapes. In the field of learning CNNs play a role in extracting and representing features from input data particularly in image analysis. The intricate layers of the network can learn patterns and hierarchical representations. One notable example in the realm of CNNs is the ResNet50 architecture, renowned for its ability to handle neural networks—a cornerstone, within deep learning.

II. CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS

A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) finds extensive application in image-based processing, including tasks like classification, detection, and image segmentation. The CNN's architecture is structured around multiple layers known as convolutional layers. These layers excel at feature extraction from query images, encompassing attributes like color, dimensions, and other visual elements.

The feature extraction process within a CNN is primarily executed through its convolutional layers. Once these layers extract the necessary features, they proceed to one or more fully connected layers, responsible for tasks such as classification and regression, built upon these features.

This neural network framework simplifies the task of extracting image features from predefined image datasets using a concise codebase. CNN, short for Convolutional Neural Network, stands as a crucial subfield within the domain of neural networks, prominently employed in image and video recognition, as well as classification tasks. CNNs consist of distinct layers: convolutional layers, pooling layers, and other fully connected layers.

Convolutional layers operate by employing a mathematical operation known as convolution, strategically used to extract crucial image features. These layers intake the input image and use a set of filters, often termed kernels, to generate a feature map. These filters specialize in recognizing specific patterns in images, such as edges and corners, and the resulting feature map accentuates the locations where these patterns are detected.

Pooling layers play a pivotal role in spatial dimension reduction within the feature maps, implementing a downsampling procedure. This operation not only simplifies the computational complexity of the network but also serves as a countermeasure against overfitting.

Fully connected layers are conventionally positioned toward the conclusion of the network architecture for image classification. They take the features derived from convolutional and pooling layers, providing an output in the form of a probability distribution over potential classes. In the current context, our focus is directed away from numerous fully connected layers, with an emphasis solely on the outcomes of feature extraction.

Fig 1

Fig 2

The neural network illustrated in [Figure 1] and [Figure 2] provides a visual representation of the ResNet50 convolutional neural network architecture. CNNs possess a notable ability to grasp and infer essential image features, a capability primarily harnessed through the deployment of convolutional layers. Convolutional layers stand as the fundamental components of CNNs, serving as the cornerstones for the acquisition and extraction of feature maps from images. The CNN structure comprises three distinct layers:

Input Layer:

In the seminar project, the input layer serves as the initial stage responsible for processing the query image and extracting its distinctive features. These features are subsequently transmitted to the following layers to perform complex tasks, including classification and segmentation.

The input layer in the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) comprises a series of convolutional layers followed by multiple pooling layers. This layer applies a set of filters to the query image, facilitating the extraction of essential image features such as edges, corners, and textures. Within the CNN framework, the input layer is instrumental in the extraction of vital features from the input image data, effectively preparing it for further processing by subsequent layers.

Hidden Layer:

The hidden layers in the seminar project are devoted to feature extraction. These layers harness the power of the ResNet50 convolutional neural network architecture, an essential component of the project. In these layers, ResNet50's convolutional filters meticulously analyze the input image,

extracting an array of features across various scales. These extracted features then undergo further processing through activation functions and pooling layers, effectively reducing their dimensions and complexity.

The number of hidden layers within the CNN model can vary based on the problem's complexity and the query data's size. Typically, the CNN model comprises several convolutional layers, followed by pooling layers aimed at reducing the spatial dimensions of the extracted features. Subsequently, one or more fully connected layers are employed to execute tasks such as classification or regression based on the query images.

Output Layer:

The output layer in the seminar project typically consists of one or more fully connected layers, also known as dense layers. These layers generate a feature vector for each query image, and these features are then stored for various applications, including classification, object detection, or segmentation.

The image search engine implemented using CNN and Deep Learning encompasses several stages, including data access and preprocessing. In the project, the feature extraction process leverages the ResNet50 architecture, a prominent convolutional neural network. ResNet50's convolutional layers meticulously analyze the input image, extracting a wide array of features. Furthermore, Keras, a versatile deep learning framework, is utilized to facilitate model construction, feature vector indexing, and similarity-based image retrieval.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Surbhi Jain et al. [1], The article image-based search engine employing deep learning highlights the difficulty of studying picture data on the World Wide Web (WWW) owing to its massive nature and inability to be indexed by standard text-based approaches. Content-Based Image Retrieval (CBIR) has emerged as a solution, however it has proven challenging to create effective input techniques and get appropriate retrieval results owing to the low-level nature of observable elements in user input photographs. The semantic gap between low-level pixel data and high-level human interpretation of picture semantics is the major difficulty in CBIR systems. Machine learning (ML) has been examined as a realistic technique to narrow this gap, with deep learning methods such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) showing promise in improving feature representations and similarity metrics.

The study focuses on the applications of CNNs model in classification and retrieval issues, using transfer learning utilizing the GoogleNet deep architecture for retrieval of comparable pictures. Each picture's feature vectors were the last fully connected layer from the retrained GoogleNet CNN model, and Euclidean distances between these vectors and those of the query image were computed to determine the dataset's closest matches. Overall, the paper demonstrates the

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potential of CNNs and transfer learning in enhancing the performance of CBIR systems, notably in minimizing the semantic gap between low-level visual data and high-level human interpretation of picture semantics.

I Gede Susrama Mas Diyasa et al. [2], The article reverse image search analysis based on pre-trained convolutional neural network model describes the application of Reverse Image Search (RIS), which is a form of Content-Based Image

Retrieval (CBIR), and how it may be used to search for information by entering photos as queries. The author utilizes a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model to extract picture characteristics from RIS findings and compares the performance of the Pre-Trained CNN Model technique with standard methods such as perceptual hashing.

The author emphasizes that the Pre-Trained CNN Model technique can handle orientation information, which is a shortcoming of perceptual hashing. However, the Euclidean distance from the feature vector of various photographs was relatively close, even though the images were distinct. This shows that there may be some limits to the usefulness of the Pre-Trained CNN Model approach.

Overall, the study gives insights into the possibilities of RIS and CBIR to enhance the search experience for users. However, it also underscores the necessity for continued study to develop these approaches and solve their shortcomings.

Divya Ragatha Venkata et al. [3], The article image query based search engine employing picture content retrieval introduces an innovative notion of using photos as a query for search engines, which is becoming increasingly common in today's technology-driven world. This article explains the functioning of a picture search engine model that allows users to enter photographs from their local database and then they acquired information about these images from the internet.

This article outlines the difficulties associated with utilizing pictures as queries and how the suggested approach attempts to address these difficulties. The use of image-based comparison and analysis methods is suggested as the remedy for the complexity of using query pictures for information retrieval.

The study's findings show that the suggested model extracts picture content and retrieves pertinent data with effectiveness. One of the best uses for this search engine concept is considered to be product database searches.

Overall, the research adds something worthwhile to the area of image-based search methods, and the model that is produced may find use in a number of scenarios. However, the text is devoid of extensive technical and other details on how the model works, which would have been very helpful to academics and other stakeholders.

Enescu Magda Florentina and others [4], This research uses color descriptors to compare various color spaces and color picture search techniques. The trials are well recorded, and graphs and

charts are used to clearly show the findings. The investigation concludes that RGB color spaces yielded subpar results and that HSV color space performs better than other color spaces. The study only looks at color descriptors; other visual aspects are not examined, however the work offers insightful information for further investigations. All things considered, the article is instructive and offers helpful details on how various color spaces and picture search techniques work.

Kita Kenji et al. [5], This study covers the use of a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to create a picture search engine for the fashion sector. With the use of a unique dataset, the writers trained their own CNN and attained excellent accuracy. They constructed a reverse search engine using the Euclidean and Cosine distances. The results demonstrated that the accuracy of the trained CNN model determines the accuracy and precision of the image search system. The study emphasizes the significance of precise picture attributes and offers insightful information on using CNNs for image search. All things considered, the study is instructive and offers a practical method for image search in the fashion business.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In the proposed methodology of the seminar project, the system initiates the process by conducting feature extraction on both the images within the database and the query image. This feature extraction procedure leverages a specialized algorithm rooted in convolutional neural networks (CNNs). The algorithm thoroughly analyzes and discerns the unique attributes and characteristics embedded in each image, subsequently translating these traits into a series of numerical values that encapsulate the image's distinctive features. Moreover, the features extracted from the query images play a pivotal role in the subsequent indexing process alongside the database images.

With the feature extraction complete, the system proceeds to the next crucial step: calculating the similarity between the query image and every image stored within the database. This similarity assessment hinges on a meticulous comparison of the feature vectors associated with each image, allowing for a precise quantification of the degree of similarity.

Upon receipt of the query image, the system initiates a comprehensive search to identify all images that exhibit a significant resemblance to the query image. These identified images are then methodically sorted and ranked based on their individual similarity scores, with the highest-ranking matches emerging as the top recommendations. The entire workflow is visually depicted in [Fig 3].

Fig 3

The images used for comparison is retrieved from the specific folder where all the database images stored in [Fig 4] we retrieve all the images to a specific folder and further this folder is used for its feature extraction.

```
import os
import numpy as np
from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing import image
from tensorflow.keras.applications.vgg16 import VGG16
from tensorflow.keras.applications.vgg16 import preprocess_input
from tensorflow.keras.applications.vgg16 import decode_predictions

root_image_path = "/Users/kenji/Desktop/kenji"
root_feature_path = "/Users/kenji/Desktop/kenji"

# Path of Deep Feature
def folder_to_image(folder):
    list_dir = folder + "/" + name for name in os.listdir(folder) if name.endswith(".jpg") or name.endswith(".png") or name.endswith(".jpeg")
    n = 0
    image_list = []
    image_path = []
    for path in list_dir:
        n += 1
        image = image.load_img(path, target_size=(224, 224))
        image_np = np.array(preprocess_input(image))
        image_path.append(path)
    return (n, image_list, image_path)

def folder_to_image_list(folder):
    list_dir = folder + "/" + name for name in os.listdir(folder) if name.endswith(".jpg") or name.endswith(".png") or name.endswith(".jpeg")
    n = 0
    image_list = []
    image_path = []
    for path in list_dir:
        n += 1
        image = image.load_img(path, target_size=(224, 224))
        image_np = np.array(preprocess_input(image))
        image_path.append(path)
    return (n, image_list, image_path)

def folder_to_image_list(folder):
    list_dir = folder + "/" + name for name in os.listdir(folder) if name.endswith(".jpg") or name.endswith(".png") or name.endswith(".jpeg")
    n = 0
    image_list = []
    image_path = []
    for path in list_dir:
        n += 1
        image = image.load_img(path, target_size=(224, 224))
        image_np = np.array(preprocess_input(image))
        image_path.append(path)
    return (n, image_list, image_path)
```

Fig 4

Using Convolutional Neural Networks and TensorFlow with ResNet50 as the backbone, the features of all images in the specific folder are extracted. Subsequently, these features are saved in another folder in .npy format, as depicted in [Fig 5].

```
import tensorflow as tf
from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing import image
from tensorflow.keras.applications.vgg16 import VGG16
from tensorflow.keras.applications.vgg16 import preprocess_input
from tensorflow.keras.applications.vgg16 import decode_predictions

# Class of Feature Extraction with ResNet50 backbone
class FeatureExtractor:
    def __init__(self):
        self.model = VGG16(weights='imagenet', include_top=False)
        self.model.compile(optimizer='adam', loss='categorical_crossentropy', metrics=['accuracy'])

    def extract_features(self, image_path):
        image = image.load_img(image_path, target_size=(224, 224))
        image_np = np.array(preprocess_input(image))
        model_output = self.model.predict(image_np)
        return model_output

# Feature Extraction Function
def extract_features(image_path):
    extractor = FeatureExtractor()
    features = extractor.extract_features(image_path)
    return features
```

Fig 5

To facilitate the comparison of the query image with the existing images, the initial step involves extracting features from all images in the database and storing them for future reference. The user's input provides the query image, and utilizing the same feature extraction class, the features of the query image are also extracted and stored in a designated folder. The acquisition of the query image is facilitated through the user interface, as depicted in [Fig 6].

Fig 6

Euclidean distance serves as a widely adopted distance metric for comparing image features. In the realm of computer vision and image processing, features play a pivotal role in characterizing various aspects of an image, encompassing attributes such as color, texture, shape, size, and more.

When it comes to comparing two images based on their features, the Euclidean distance emerges as the go-to measure for gauging similarity between the feature vectors of these images. The calculation of Euclidean distance entails taking the square root of the total sum of squared differences between corresponding elements present in both feature vectors.

In the quest to identify images similar to a query image, one can compute the distance between the query image and each image within the dataset. This is achieved using the Euclidean distance or L2 norm formula. A smaller resulting value indicates a higher degree of similarity to the query image, aiding in the retrieval of similar images.

$$dist(q, img) = ||q - img||_2 = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (q_i - img_i)^2}$$

The formula involves several key variables: "q" representing the query, "img" representing the image, "n" denoting the number of items in the feature vector, and "i" indicating the vector's position.

Searching for similar images within a vast image collection is a common application of image search. Identifying images with the closest distances to the query image begins with calculating the distances between the feature vectors of each image in the collection.

The feature vector comprises a set of values extracted from an image. Multiple feature vectors can represent an image's attributes, such as its color histogram or other texture features. Once we generate a feature vector for an image, assessing the similarity of images becomes straightforward by calculating the distance between these feature vectors and the features of the query image.

Several distance metrics are available for computing the distances between feature vectors of the query image and the images in the dataset. These metrics encompass the Euclidean distance, Manhattan distance, and others. In Python, we leverage the NumPy library to efficiently perform these calculations.

NumPy, a Python library for scientific computing, offers an array of functionalities and tools for working with arrays and matrices. NumPy enables the creation and manipulation of arrays of feature vectors and facilitates distance calculations between these arrays.

Additionally, the process leverages ResNet50, further enhancing the feature extraction capabilities

In the system, the resulting image is typically displayed based on the calculated similarity between the query image and a set of images stored in the specific folder. The top results are those images that are closest to the query image. The system also displays the degree of similarity for each image in relation to the query image. If the query image is present within the image dataset, the displayed similarity is 100%, and the degree of similarity for other images may vary accordingly. In the [Fig 7] shows the results similar for query image. Here we limited the results to shows the most similar ones and if there is no similar images is found then displayed as no result found. In [Fig 7] it shows most similar images and the first image is exactly similar to the query image and have the accuracy 100% and other images have bit lesser accuracy than first one.

Fig 7

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion this project utilizes ResNet50, which's a deep convolutional neural network (CNN), along with TensorFlow and NumPy to help with image similarity searches. The method relies on calculating the distance between images to identify the similar matches. When the query image closely aligns with the existing dataset this approach provides results. However, if the query image significantly differs from the dataset the accuracy of the results may be compromised. It's important to note that while this technique doesn't guarantee a match for the query image it excels at identifying the comparable images within the dataset. ResNet50 plays a role, in enhancing feature extraction and assessing similarity in this image search system through its advanced deep learning capabilities.

VI. REFERENCES

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